

FERTILIZERS OBTAINED FROM NON-NATURAL RAW MATERIALS AND THEIR TYPES

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Annotation. *This in the article from waste composting method with unconventional fertilizers preparation them disposal of doing the most efficient method considered, it is at once three the problem solution does First, organic fertilizer the problem; secondly, the soil food elements with enrichment and thirdly, the environment of the environment waste with from contamination storage issues own the solution finds*

Key words: *Hummus, non-traditional, farming, enterprises leftovers, household service , apartment waste, sweet water cloudy, in autumn spilled a tree leaves*

Introduction

Unconventional fertilizer different organic leftovers microorganisms activity as a result from decay fruit has been important local fertilizers is considered To the soil to be given unconventional fertilizer of plants growth and development for different different conditions creates

Soils properties improve and productivity in raising fertilizers main factor is considered Fertilizers into 2 groups to be can: traditional and unconventional. Traditional fertilizers - in agriculture apply to tradition turning around the rest, industry scale removable and local in the circumstances there is has been are fertilizers . Such to fertilizers in factories work excretory mineral and

microfertilizers, livestock and poultry manure, green fertilizers enters Unconventional fertilizers in farming of fertilizers new type they are different waste and from the remains composting the way with is obtained [1].

Our country village in the farm traditional to fertilizers has been Demand high is some _ cases their lack of observed . For example , Uzbekistan conditions hummus balance without deficit in case holding stand up for each one hectares irrigated to the ground each 17-18 tons per year organic fertilizer application need But for now this in quantity organic fertilizers collect opportunity no

Statistics to information than , har year village farm nitrogenous to fertilizers has been demand 70-80%, phosphorus to fertilizers has been 30-40% of the demand is being met . From this come coming out conclusion that is, to the soil to give possible to be organic mass and food of elements addition sources to find need That 's it to sources industry and village economy work release waste, village farm products again work of enterprises leftovers, household service, rice cookers, apartment waste, sweet water cloudy, in autumn spilled a tree leaves bacterial preparations and etc. enters Of these in the composition a lot amount, in some cases up to 50% organic substances , macro - and trace elements, enzymes and plants growth for necessary has been another substances will be

Unconventional in fertilization applied organic fertilizers preparation for in Uzbekistan enough amount raw material there is Current at the time in Uzbekistan each 30 million per year. tons city hard household and industry waste, tree leave khazons collecting water basins 2 billion under from the ton more than there is a fuzzy (il) [2]. This of waste a lot part open in the fields is stored and from per year they are occupied field increased is going And this surroundings of the environment contamination probability more increases . That's why for this waste disposal to do is an urgent issue. In this from waste composting method with unconventional fertilizers preparation them disposal of doing the most efficient method considered, it is at once three the problem solution does[3]. First, organic fertilizer the problem; secondly , the soil food elements with enrichment and

thirdly, the environment of the environment waste with from contamination storage issues own the solution finds _ This waste composting the way with disposal to do in farming food substances balance in order in comparison, waste contained food of elements substances exchange in the chain participation when it comes important place holds A number of organomineral fertilizers are organomineral fertilizers obtained on the basis of local raw materials and nitrogen-fixing microorganisms [4-12].

Methods.

In order to quickly and easily achieve the intended goal in conducting scientific research and conducting experiments, first of all, it is necessary to know how to correctly choose the methods of analysis. In particular, it is advisable to use fast, modern and, of course, highly accurate analytical methods to determine various physico-chemical parameters of raw materials and finished products in the production of non-traditional fertilizers based on local raw materials.

Cattle and poultry manure, straw, cow dung, tree leaves, fresh water turbidity, samples of coal industry waste were used as the main raw materials for scientific research. The main chemical composition of these raw materials is presented in Table 1.

Table 1.

Amount of nutrients in common waste and residues in Uzbekistan.

Waste and leftovers	Organic mass	Air in humidity mass ratio in %			20t mass quantity (kg)			
		N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	N	P ₂ O ₅	K ₂ O	Organics (kg)
Cattle manure	60	0.50	0.25	0.60	100	50	120	12000
In poultry manure	66	2.06	1.80	1.10	412.0	360	220	13200

Straw	93.5	0.46	0.20	0.90	92.0	40.0	180	18700
Gozapoya	91.6	1.13	0.42	1.25	226	84	250	18200
A tree leaf	88.2	0.37	0.24	0.27	74.0	48	54	17640
Chuchuk water blurry	40.4	0.58	0.18	0.69	116.0	36	138	8000
Lignin	91.5	0.18	0.024	0.021	36	4.8	4.2	18200
Coal industry remains	30.1	0.33	0.27	0.28	66	54	56	6000
City waste waters sedimentation	31.5	0.198	2.87	0.39	39.6	168	78	6600
City hard waste	26.2	0.50	0.41	0.62	100	82	124	5240

Unconventional of fertilizers advantage that is, first of all, they free raw material at the expense of is taken; second, place in itself prepared due to transportation costs less, thirdly, environment environment always clean in case held, fourth, in the composition in traditional mineral fertilizers no food substances that it was for soil properties Well done, village economy crops productivity increases . They are own in the composition plant nutrition for necessary has been macro and trace elements keeps Compost each one gardener for replace which cannot be is fertilizer . Own your hands with how by doing compost to do need Own your hands with compost from preparation before, you storage place about decision acceptance to do should, often wood box is used. Him own your hands with of wood to do can First layer a tree leaves will be sawed off. This components of the box bottom to the part about 10 centimeters in height placement need

Results .

From us laboratory studies were carried out on the effect of various additives on natural beneficial agricultural and rice wastes, as well as on the production of non-conventional fertilizers containing cattle manure and various poultry wastes. Cattle dung, paddy waste and paddy The quantities of organic fertilizers obtained based on waste were studied. For this, cattle manure: paddy waste and rice waste were taken in the ratio of 100 : 25:10, and the chemical composition of the obtained mixture was studied in the composting process in the ratio of 100 : (25-35): (10-15).

Cattle dung, paddy waste and paddy Chemical composition of non-traditional fertilizer samples obtained on the basis of waste (CD: PW: PCh=100: (25-35) : (10-15))

CD: PW: PCh	P ₂ O ₅ um. , %	CaO general , %	O S , %	HA , %	FA, %	WSO M , %	K ₂ O, %	N general . %	Humidi ty , %
100 : 25 :10	0.343	0.555	30.7 9	3.8 0	3.93	2.78	0.54 6	0.350	66.20
100: 28: 12	0.442	0.585	30.7 0	3.7 9	3.92	2.77	0.54 4	0.389	66.34
100 : 30 : 13	0.541	0.652	3 0.61	3.7 8	3.91	2.75	0.54 2	0.4 0 7	66.48
100 : 33 : 14	0.639	0.6 69	30,4 4	3.7 6	3.88	2.73	0.53 7	0.445	66,76
100 : 35 : 25	0.737	0.736	31.2 7	3.7 3	3.86	2.71	0.53 3	0.502	67.04

in organic fertilizers obtained in acceptable sizes are as follows (wt., %): P₂O_{5um.} - 0.737; organic substances - 31.27; humic acids - 3.73; fulvic acids - 3.86; water-soluble organic matter - 2.71; nitrogen - 0.533; humidity - 67.04. In this case, the loss of non-traditional substances will be 12.02 % and the level of

humification will be equal to 78.08 %.

Discussion.

From the point of view of agrochemical and economic efficiency, the ratio of CD: PW: PCh when it is 100: (25-35): (10-15) can be taken as an acceptable ratio and the compost maturation time as in the previous case is 90 days. In this case, we can observe that the total amount of nitrogen, humic acids, fulvic acids P_2O_5 increases accordingly.

Conclusion.

Along with all the nutrients (macro- and microelements) necessary for the plant, a large amount of microorganisms fall into the soil as well as non-traditional fertilizers. This microorganisms soil microflora enriched, his in the composition passing microbiological processes (rotting, mineralization, ammonification). activates. Such from fertilizers reasonable use village economy for very important the fact that obvious apparently is standing

Compost of vegetables growth and development acceleration for necessary Organic fertilizers the soil productivity and harvest efficiency increases. From this besides, gardeners most of the time not only organic from the dogs, maybe they use minerals as well they are very a lot in quantity micro to the elements have organic fertilizers are basically organic compounds in the form of plant feed own into received fertilizers. To these manure, composts, peat, grass fertilizer and others enters

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